

Dyeing of Cotton Fabric with Different Shade% of Reactive Dyes and Different Stripping Condition to Find out the Maximum –Minimum Percentage of Strength Loss, Weight Loss, and Pilling Resistance of Stripped Fabric.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

There are lots of key and slight problems of textile dyeing industries such as shade variation or dyeing faults and establishment of hue spots on the cloth external through coloring and downstream treating of textiles materials. Such problems in the delivery quality of fabric are generally attacked through a Hydrose and Caustic chemical stripping process which is a common practice in dyeing industries for the medium to dark shade batches. However, reactive dyes cannot be stripped satisfactorily from cellulosic materials due to the development of co-valent bonds between dye and fiber. This research was undertaken using 1.5% and 3% reactive dyes on R.F.D cotton fabric and dye sample stripping was carried out in different time and Temperature alkali reductive stripping process. The main objective of the work was to find the best stripping quality of cotton fabric. To find out the Strength loss, weight loss, and pilling resistance of stripped fabric were considered. When the increase of Time, temperature & concentration (Hydrose & Caustic) of stripping chemicals, the stripping percentages were improved; if stripping chemicals, processing time and temperature will much higher than the fibre or fabric damage will be occurred. So, we need to select optimum or suitable stripping Chemical, time and temperature.

Keywords: COTTON FABRIC, REACTIVE DYES, K/S VALUE, STRIPPING %, STRENGTH LOSS, WEIGHT LOSS, PILLING

Introduction

Cotton is the most important natural textile fiber in the world, as well as cellulosic textile fiber used in the manufacturing of clothes, home and industrial products. Cotton was around 40 per cent of the fiber consumed worldwide in 2004(1). Cotton is primarily grown for fiber but is also a food (cotton seed)-the main end uses for cotton seeds are vegetable oil for human consumption; whole seeds, meals, and hull for animal feed; and linters for padding and chemical cellulose. Cotton fibers are originated from seed hairs of Malvales plants, Malvaceae family, Gossypieae tribe and Gossypium genus. There are four major domesticated cotton species of commercial *hirsutum*, *barbadense*, *aboreum* and *harbaseum* in botanical form. Thirty-three species are currently acknowledged but all but these four are non-commercially recognized wild shrubs. Each of the commercially important contains several different varieties produced through breeding programs to develop cotton with continuously improving properties (e.g., faster maturation, improved yields, and enhanced insect and disease resistance) and fibers with greater length, strength, and durability(2). This group includes the Egyptian, American – Egyptian and Sea Island commercial cotton varieties. Today Egypt and Sudan are the world’s leading producers of ELS cottons. Pima, which is also ELS cotton, is a complex hybrid of Egyptian and American Upland strains and grows in the western United States (mainly California with some in Arizona, southwest Texas, and New Mexico), as well as in South America(3). Pima has many of the features of quality Egyptian cottons. The other commercial varieties-*Gossypium aboreum* and *Gossypium herbaceum*, both diploids-are collectively referred as “Desi” cottons and are the short staple cottons of Asia or the old World. Such rough cottons are the shorter grown staple cottons (ranging from 0.375 to 0.75 inches (9.5–19 mm)) and are coarse compared to American Upland varieties (micronaire value greater than 6.0). Both are of limited worldwide commercial importance, but are still commercially produced in Pakistan and India. *G. Aboreum* is also commercially grown in Burma, Bangladesh, Thailand and Vietnam. That cotton fiber is a single, elongated, complete cell which develops inside the cotton seed cells of the surface layer. Normally mature cotton fiber is a dead, hollow, cell wall is dried. In the dried out fiber, the tubular structure folds and twists, resulting in cotton fiber convolutions that separate cotton fibers from all other types of cotton hair and indirectly responsible for many of the unique features of cotton(4).

Batch wise or Exhaust Dyeing Processes

The essential guideline in the batch wise coloring process is to exhaust or penetrate however much of the color as could be expected onto the fiber utilizing impartial or partially acidic conditions, preceding facilitating the fixation step(5). The initial dyebath contains a color totally solubilised in water, a solubilizing operator, for example, urea, and an electrolyte, for example, regular salt or Glauber’s salt(6). Under these conditions, the color doesn’t respond or responds at a regular time interval and leveling happens. The pH of the dye bath is then expanded by the expansion of salt so

the color fiber fixation happens. The specific kind of reactive color being utilized normally administers the decision of selecting temperature. The final procedure is the wash off procedure, which evacuates unfixed color, salt and electrolyte(7). These dyeing operations are regularly partitioned into four unique classifications. Three of these are described on the basis of the form of exhaustion and fixation stages and the fourth is an All-In strategy.

The basic strides for reactive dye from a dye bath include the exhaustion of color from the dye bath to the fiber surface; the adsorption of color at the fiber surface; the dissemination of color from the fiber surface into the pore of the fiber; the relocation of color to give color consistency. Relocation happens when a consistency is emerged between the color in the arrangement and the color in the fiber. Fixation to cellulose happens for the most part under soluble conditions though fixation to polyamide can be accomplished under delicately acidic conditions. During the fixation phenomena, competing hydrolysis of reactive color likewise happens, when the color responds with hydroxide particles in the dye bath. Since the hydrolyzed color is generally very much similar as the fundamental reactive color in dispersion and adsorption properties, it depletes alongside the reactive structure onto the fiber surface(8). Now and again, the hydrolyzed color is held constantly on the fiber surface through physical bonding features of a direct dye on cotton. The hydrolysis of reactive colors brings about a level of fixation under 100%(9). Subsequent to coloring, the unfixed, hydrolyzed color must be expelled from the fiber by means of a wash off procedure, to upgrade crock fastness and wash fastness. In practical dyeing operation, fixation prevails over hydrolysis because of significant variables(10). Fundamentally, cellulose has a lower segregation constant than water, bringing about roughly a 25-overlay overabundance of cellulosate particles over hydroxyl particles. Furthermore, the partiality of the color for the fiber lessens the measure of color accessibility for hydrolysis in the dye bath. Thirdly, the pH inside the fiber is fundamentally kept up by cellulose particles and the charge on the fiber surface removes hydroxide particles from the fiber inside(11).

Nucleophilic substitution

Nucleophilic substitution describes color fiber fixation that happens when a leaving bunch in the reactive framework is dislodged because of a collaboration with a nucleophilic bunch on the polymer chain. The response of a monochlorotriazine reactive color with a hydroxy gathering of cellulose and additionally an amino gathering of keratin is average example of this procedure which is shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2

Figure 1. Reaction of a monochlorotriazine dye with cellulose.

Figure 2. Hydrolysis of a monochlorotriazine dye

Nucleophilic addition

Nucleophilic option describes the color fiber response in which a nucleophilic bunch in the fiber includes over an initiated carbon-carbon two sided bond in the reactive group(12). A large portion of reactive frameworks utilized contain a vinyl sulphone moiety. The vinylsulphone reactive gathering itself is normally not present in business type of the colors utilized(13). Rather, progressively stable forerunner, for example, the β -sulphatoethylsulphone group is utilized. The two-step procedure related with fiber fixation. Fundamentally related colors containing a β -sulphatoethylsulphamoyl bunch most likely structure a cyclic compound equipped for responding with cellulose to give cellulose ether. Frameworks dependent on enacted double bonds additionally experience a serious hydrolysis response.

Figure 3. Fixation via nucleophilic addition to a vinylsulphone dye

Materials and methods

Pretreated (Scoured-bleached) cotton fabric (Plain weave) of about 255 g/m² (Yarn count 20 ×16/128×60), supplied by H.H Textiles Mills Ltd., Borpa, Rupgonj, Narayangonj was used throughout the study. Used famous chemicals company Color root's chemicals & Some famous German's chemicals, those are Wetting agent, Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Carbonate, Stabilizer, Detergent Collected from Huntsman Bangladesh Ltd. Reactive Dye (MCT-VS), Reactive Dye (MFT-VS), (and vinyl sulphone) reactive dyes: Remazol (active double bond, 40°C, combined shade percentage was 1.5% and also Remazol combined shade 3% was used for this research purpose. Hydrose was used as a stripping agent, it was also collected from Sinha Textile Mills Ltd. Kachpur, Rupgonj, Narayangong. All other chemicals and auxiliaries used for the experimental work were laboratory grade reagents.

Dyeing process

Dyeing was carried out on the pretreated fabric with the two shades (1.5% and 3%) using combination shade in exhaust method in the IR sample dyeing machine at 60°C for 40 min, keeping material to liquor ratio 1:10 and pH 10.5. Then after washing, the dyed fabric was neutralized with 1 g/l acetic acid followed by soaping with 1 g/l Dekol SN at 80°C for 5 min. Dyeing recipes for different shade % of reactive dyes was given in Table 1.

Table. Dyeing recipes using 1.5% and 3% reactive dyes.

Serial No.	Shade %			Recipe			
	Dyes name	Combined shade %	Individual shade	Glauber salt g/L	Soda Ash g/L	Wetting agent g/L	Sequestering agent g/L
1.	Remazol Red	1.5 %	1.0%	45	8	1	1
	Remazol Yellow		0.4%				
	Remazol Blue		0.1%				
2.	Remazol Red	3%	2.0%	80	12	1	1
	Remazol Yellow		1.0%				

Stripping process

Eight different stripping operations (see Table 2) were carried out for each shade% in the sample dyeing machine using material to liquor ratio 1:15 for 30 min.

Table. 2 Stripping recipes

Stripping operation	Temp (°C)	Conc. of sodium hydrosulphite (g/l)	Conc. of caustic soda (g/l)
1.	70	12	6
2		12	12
3		24	12
4		24	24
5	85	12	6
6		12	12
7		24	12
8		24	24

Fabric stripping percentage

Stripping percentage

The color yields of both dyed and stripped fabric were determined in terms of K/S value by a dual beam reflectance spectrophotometer. The stripping percentage was calculated by using below in equation 1.

Stripping Percentage= $\frac{\text{K/S value of dyed sample} - \text{K/S value of stripped sample}}{\text{K/S value of dyed sample}} * 100$(1)

Fabric quality evaluation

Strength loss

Tensile strength of dyed and stripped fabric was carried out in ISO 13938–1:1999 method by Tensile strength Tester. Then strength loss of the stripped sample which is shown by equation (2),

Strength loss % = $\frac{\text{Fabric strength before stripping} - \text{Fabric strength after stripping}}{\text{Fabric strength before stripping}} * 100$(2)

Weight loss

Loss in weight of stripped sample was measured by difference in weight before and after treatment using equation (3).

Weight loss % = $\frac{\text{Fabric weight before stripping} - \text{Fabric weight after stripping}}{\text{Fabric weight before stripping}} * 100$(3)

Pilling Resistance

Pilling resistance of stripped fabric samples was assessed in SN 198525 method using Pilling Tester.

Result Discussion

To estimate dyeing performance, the color strength (K/S) and CIELAB of the cotton plain woven dyed samples were dignified using a Data color 400 spectro-photometer through illuminant D65 and 100 observer. The K/S value is intended by the Kubelka–Munk calculation, $K/S = (1 - R) / 2R$, where R is the reflectance, K is the immersion quantity, and S is the sprinkle coefficient(14).

The color variation is expressed as ΔE^* and is designed by Equation 4.

$$\Delta E^* = \sqrt{(\Delta L^*)^2 + (\Delta a^*)^2 + (\Delta b^*)^2} \quad (4)$$

Where ΔE^* is the CIELAB hue variance amongst batch then standard. Now ΔL^* , Δa^* , Δb^* and hence ΔE^* remain in proportionate parts. ΔL^* signifies the difference among lightness (where $L^* = 100$) then darkness (where $L^* = 0$), Δa^* the difference between red (+ a^*) and green (- a^*) and Δb^* the difference between yellow (+ b^*) and blue (- b^*). For the study, the amount of levelness was defined according to ΔE . All dignified samples indicated a maximum immersion wavelength value (λ_{max}) at 444 nm.

Stripping percentage

Stripping percentages of the dyed fabrics for 1.5% and 3% shades which are shown below in Figure 4 and Figure 5 accordingly

Figure. 4 Stripping percentages of dyed fabric (1.5% shade).

Figure. 5 Stripping percentages of dyed fabric (3 % shade).

From Figure 4, for 1.5% shade, it was found that stripping percentages of dyed fabrics increased gradually with the increase of concentration of stripping chemicals (Hydrose and caustic soda) when fabrics were stripped both at 70°C and 85°C. Stripping percentages were also found higher at 85°C than 70°C under each combination of stripping chemicals. As the temperature of the stripping operation was more, the stripping was more. Both at 70°C and 85°C temperature when concentration of caustic soda was doubled from Figure 4, for 6g/l to 12 g/l with 12 g/L Hydrose as well as from 12 g/l to 24 g/l with 24 g/l Hydrose, stripping percentages were increased rapidly. From above Figure 5, similar trends were found for 3% shade. Using 24g/l Hydrose and 24g/l caustic soda and stripping at 85°C, the maximum stripping for 1.5% and 3% shades were found 96.49% and 97.88 respectively.

Strength loss

Strength loss percentages of the dyed fabrics for 1.5% and 3% shades were shown in Figures 6 and 7 respectively.

Figure. 6 Strength loss % of stripped samples (1.5% shades)

In case of 1.5% shade, strength loss percentages were increased gradually with the increase of concentration of stripping chemicals both at 70°C and 85°C as shown in above Figure 6. In between 70°C and 85°C, it was noticed that strength loss percentages were higher at 85°C when the fabrics were treated in same parameter. Here, the sample dyed with 1.5% shade when treated with 24 g/l Hydrose and 24 g/l caustic soda at 85°C showed maximum strength loss of 9.59% in comparison to the maximum strength loss of 9.38% when treated at 70°C under the same combination of stripping chemicals. As both the temperature and stripping chemicals were comparatively more, the extent of strength loss was also found more. Again, when caustic soda was doubled from 6 g/l to 12 g/l with 12 g/l Hydrose, strength losses were increased from 4.78% to 5.77% (In case of 70°C) and from 4.86 to 6.55% (In case of 85°C). Similarly, increasing caustic soda from 12 g/l to 24 g/l with 24 g/l Hydrose resulted in increased strength loss from 7.85% to 9.38% (In case of 70°C) and from 8.88% to 9.59% (In case of 85°C).

Figure. 7 Strength loss% of stripped samples (1.5% shades)

For 3% shade, similar trends of gradual increasing of strength loss with the increase of concentrations of stripping chemicals were found as shown in above Figure 7 for both 70°C and 85°C. The samples dyed with 3% shade when stripped using 24 g/l Hydrose and 24 g/l caustic soda at 85°C showed maximum strength loss of % in 11.85 comparisons to the maximum strength loss of 10.55% when treated at 70°C under the same combination of stripping chemicals.

Weight loss

Quality of stripped fabric was also evaluated by measuring the percent weight loss. Weight loss percentages of the dyed fabrics for 1.5% and 3% shades were displayed in below Figures 8 and 9, respectively. From Figure 8, for 1.5% shade it was noticed that weight loss percentages of stripped fabrics increased with the increase of concentration of stripping chemicals when fabrics were stripped both at 70°C showed maximum weight loss of 4.88 and 85°C showed maximum weight loss of 5.85. The weight loss percentages were found higher at 85°C than 70°C under each combination of stripping chemicals used. As the temperature of stripping operations was more, the weight loss percentage was found more.

Figure. 8 Weight loss% of stripped samples (1.5% shades)

In case of 3% shade, similar trend was found as shown in above Figure 9 The samples dyed with 3% shade when stripped using 24 g/l Hydrose and 24 g/l caustic soda at 85°C showed maximum weight loss of 6.97% in comparison to the maximum weight loss of 5.94 % when treated at 70°C under the same combination of stripping chemicals.

Figure. 9 Weight loss% of stripped samples (3% shade)

The alcohol groups on the glucose units in the cellulose backbone of cotton act as a weak acid and are ionized under alkaline conditions. As cotton fibers partially dissolve in concentrated sodium hydroxide at elevated temperatures, fabric strength loss occurred. As such, during alkaline dye reductive process fabric strength loss occurred. Strength loss of stripped fabric increased with the increase of stripping action provided by the elevated temperature and concentration of Hydrose and caustic soda. Increased weight losses of stripped fabrics are the consequences of higher strength loss due to similar way.

Ratings were found similar as dyed fabric when 12 g/l Hydrose and 6 g/l caustic soda

**Ratings for dyed and stripped samples in case of 1.5% shade
1.5 % shade (Pilling resistance at 70 °C)**

Pilling resistance ratings were found 5, 4-5 and 4 under 125, 500 and 2000 cycles for dyed fabric with 1.5% dyes as shown in Table 3.

	125 cycle	500 cycle	2000 cycle
Dyed Sample	5	4-5	4
H-12gm & CS 6 gm/L	5	4-5	4
H-12gm & CS 12 gm/L	4-5	4	3-4
H-24gm & CS 12 gm/L	4-5	4	3-4
H- 24gm & CS 24 gm/L	4-5	4	3-4

combination were used at 70°C but ratings decreased by 1/2 grade than the dyed fabric for 500 and 2000 cycles under same combination of chemicals at 70 °C. Similar to 12 gm/L Hydrose and 12 gm/L caustic soda combination were used at 70°C but ratings decreased by 1/2 grade than the dyed fabric for 500 and 2000 cycles. In other two parameters Hydrose 24 g/L and Caustic 12 g/L ratings were found 4-5, 4, and 3-4 and of 24 g/l Hydrose and 24 g/l caustic soda, ratings were found 4-5, 4, and 3-4 when treated at 125, 500 and 2000 cycles but decreased by 1/2 grade than the dyed fabric for 500 and 2000 cycles at 70°C.

1.5 % shade (Pilling resistance at 85 °C)

Pilling resistance ratings were found 5, 4-5 and 4 under 125, 500 and 2000 cycles for fabric dyed with 1.5% dyes as shown in Table 4.

	125	500	2000
Dyed Sample	5	4.5	4
H-12gm & CS 6 gm/L	5	4-5	3-4
H-12gm & CS 12 gm/L	5	4-5	3-4
H-24gm & CS 12 gm/L	4-5	4	3-4
H- 24gm & CS 24 gm/L	4-5	3-4	2-3

Ratings were found similar as dyed fabric when 12 g/l Hydrose and 6 g/l caustic soda combination were used at 85°C but ratings decreased by 1/2 grade than the dyed fabric for 500 and 2000 cycles under same combination of chemicals at 85 °C. Similar to 12 gm/L Hydrose and 12 gm/L caustic soda combination were used at 85°C but ratings decreased by 1/2 grade than the dyed fabric for 500 and 2000 cycles.

In other two parameters Hydrose 24 g/L and Caustic 12 g/L ratings were found 4-5, 4, and 3-4 and of 24 g/l Hydrose and 24 g/l caustic soda, ratings were found 4-5, 3-4, and 2-3 when treated at 125, 500 and 2000 cycles but decreased by 1 grade than the dyed fabric for 500 and 2000 cycles at 85°C.

Ratings for dyed and stripped samples in case of 3% shade

3 % shade (Pilling resistance at 70 °C)

For 3% shade, pilling resistance ratings of dyed fabric were found 5 under 125 cycles and 4-5 under 500 and 4.5 under 2000 cycles as shown in Table 5.

	125	500	2000
Dyed Sample	5	4-5	4
H-12gm & CS 6 gm/L	5	4-5	4
H-12gm & CS 12 gm/L	5	4-5	3-4
H-24gm & CS 12 gm/L	4-5	4	3-4
H- 24gm & CS 24 gm/L	4-5	4	3-4

For both the stripping temperatures, in case of 12 g/l Hydrose and 6 g/l caustic soda combination, pilling resistance ratings were 5, 4-5 and 4 under 125, 500 and 2000 cycles respectively where-as for 12 g/l Hydrose and 12 g/l caustic soda, corresponding ratings were 5, 4-5 and 3-4. When the dyed sample was treated with 24 g/l Hydrose and 12 g/l caustic soda, pilling ratings were found 4-5, 4 and 3-4 under 125, 500 and 2000 cycles and 24 g/l Hydrose and 24 g/l caustic soda, pilling ratings were also found 4-5, 4 and 3-4 under 125, 500 and 2000 cycles or at 70°C, except rating 3 -4 was found under 2000 cycles for 24 g/l Hydrose and 24 g/l caustic soda combination stripping treated at 70°C.

3 % shade (Pilling resistance at 85 °C)

For 3% shade, pilling resistance ratings of dyed fabric were found 5 under 125 cycles and 4-5 under 500 and 4.5 under 2000 cycles as shown in Table 6.

	125	500	2000
Dyed Sample	5	4-5	4.5
H-12gm & CS 6 gm/L	5	4-5	4
H-12gm & CS 12 gm/L	5	4-5	3-4
H-24gm & CS 12 gm/L	4-5	4	3-4
H- 24gm & CS 24 gm/L	4-5	3-4	2-3

For both the stripping temperatures, in case of 12 g/l Hydrose and 6 g/l caustic soda combination, pilling resistance ratings were 5, 4-5 and 4 under 125, 500 and 2000 cycles respectively where-as for 12 g/l Hydrose and 12 g/l caustic soda, corresponding ratings were 5, 4-5 and 3-4. When the dyed sample was treated with 24 g/l Hydrose and 12 g/l caustic soda, pilling ratings were found 4-5, 4 and 3-4 under 125, 500 and 2000 cycles and 24 g/l Hydrose and 24 g/l caustic soda, pilling ratings were also found 4-5, 3-4 and 2-3 under 125, 500 and 2000 cycles at 85°C, but decreased by 1 grade than the dyed fabric.

Conclusion

In this study, an investigation was carried out on alkali reductive stripping process for the cotton knit fabric dyed with Reactive combine shade 1.5% and another reactive dyes combine shade 3% concerning the working parameters as the concentration of reducing agent and caustic soda, based on two stripping temperature such as 70°C stripping % was 96.49 and 85°C stripping % was 97.88 respectively.

1. Fabric strength loss percentages increased gradually with the increase of concentration of stripping chemicals and temperature of stripping bath. The sample dyed with 1.5% when treated with 24g/l Hydrose and 24 g/l caustic soda at 70 °C & 85°C showed maximum strength loss from 9.38% to 9.59 % and 3% shades when treated with 24g/l Hydrose and 24 g/l caustic soda at 70 °C & 85°C showed maximum strength loss from 10.55% to 11.85%.

2. Fabric weight loss percentages of stripped fabrics were increased gradually with the increase of concentration of stripping chemicals and stripping temperature. The sample dyed with 1.5% treated with 24 g/l Hydrose and 24 g/l caustic soda at 70°C and 85°C maximum weight loss from 4.88 to 5.85 and 3% shades when treated with 24 g/l Hydrose and 24 g/l caustic soda at 70°C and 85°C showed maximum weight loss of 5.94% and 6.97%, respectively.

3. In most cases, stripped samples showed lower pilling resistance rating than the corresponding dyed fabric.

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